

USING MOLECULAR DYNAMICS COUPLED WITH HIGHER LENGTHSCALE SIMULATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMPROVED COMPOSITE MATRIX MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Using computational methods coupled with experiment we have established a methodology for new composite matrix formulation development that takes advantage of relations we have discovered between composite performance, the desired constituent bulk properties and the polymer matrix molecular structure. We will show how we couple the molecular dynamics component of our hierarchical multi-scale simulation approach for understanding materials behavior with the continuum level techniques. Use of molecular dynamics as an aid to thermoset matrix formulation required the development of several new techniques. A method to simulate fully dense and equilibrated high glass transition temperature and high cross-link density epoxy resins while maintaining proper stoichiometry. Means for extracting values for the critical properties such as the glass transition and the critical deformation measures of dilatation and distortion that relates to our bulk property measurement will be presented. Results of our simulations and experiments will show that improved composite performance is achievable through proper selection of the organic moiety of the amine and epoxy components of the resin system.

Keywords: Molecular Dynamics, Composite, Invariants, simulations, thermosets

INTRODUCTION

Atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) linking molecular level structural details with macroscopic bulk properties has been found to be a valuable tool in enhancing our understanding of structure/property relationships of materials. Although atomistic MD has been widely used for the study of organic and natural polymers, these studies have been mainly limited to linear, branched and end linked polymers. So far, MD studies of thermosets available in the literature are mainly at the coarse-grain level where the polymer network is treated as a bead-spring system. While generating useful insight into the dependence of the physical properties of thermosetting polymers on their cross-link networks, these studies have not been able to provide specific correlation with the chemical structure of the resin system.

Existing thermoset molecular model building methods are fairly limited and take the form of approaches that perform the chemical crosslinking with minimal consideration of chemistry or other important factors such as introduction of unphysical local stresses and topological defects mostly absent from real materials. Examples of existing capabilities include various different approaches, some based on molecular dynamics simulations that build up a network on-the-fly, with others based on taking an equilibrated polymer melt, which is examined for proximity of groups capable of reacting prior to bond formation and re-equilibration. Aspects of chemistry of the

thermoset curing to include crosslink formation are not usually supported. If material properties such as elastic constants are to be predicted, new model building tools incorporating improvements in the earlier methodologies will be essential, since the existing methods too easily generate defects such as highly strained local regions which will adversely affect any attempts to study responses to deformation. These tools will almost certainly require inclusion of the option to undo a crosslink formation should this lead to unrealistic deformation of local chain geometry.

One of the major barriers in conducting atomistic simulations of thermosets is the lack of availability of polymer builders that can build highly cross-linked networks based on specific reaction conditions and the chemistry of multi-functional monomers, incorporating both step and condensation polymerization. Initial atomistic MD simulations have employed Monte Carlo and MD distance criteria methodologies to build atomistic cross-linked epoxy networks but again these approaches have not been able to incorporate specific reaction kinetics. Along with providing a starting description of the molecular network the polymer builder should also incorporate efficient ways of generating equilibrated structures. Such a builder will facilitate the molecular modeling study of high performance resin systems both with and without nano-modification and will be a valuable tool in characterizing composites for Aerospace applications.

MATERIAL CONSIDERATIONS

Methods used for preparing a thermoset polymer structure for a molecular dynamics simulation include approaches that range from no joining of monomer ingredients to an in-situ reaction based on close approach of reactive sites. For example, Zhu et al [1] used Bisphenol-F molecules to study the interaction with single walled carbon nanotubes (CNT). They simulated mechanical performance of a long and short carbon nanotube reinforced composite and the epoxy matrix without reinforcement. Yarovsky and Evans [2] simulate the behavior of epoxy resins by creating a physical mixture of the monomer ingredients in a periodic cell. After equilibration they examine the mix for reactive sites that are within a distance appropriate for chemical reaction. They assign a "priority" for the various polymerization reactions and "chemically react" the sites and remove any small molecule products. The reacted system is then equilibrated before analysis of properties. Wu and Xu [3] also use the in-situ reaction scheme to generate a polymerized three dimensional periodic structure.

Gou et al [4] build a polymer using 18 Bisphenol-F and eight diethyltoluenediamine(DETDA) molecules. They include intramolecular cyclic structures and since the mixture is not quite stoichiometric, there will be some unreacted epoxies. Mijovic and Zhang [5] build a polymer fragment using 25 Bisphenol-A and 10 diethylenetriamine molecules. The ratio used is stoichiometric and based on the structure described it would appear that the polymer has no intramolecular or cyclic linkages.

Fan and Yuen [6] construct three separate configurations of a polymer using 12, 18 or 24 molecules of Bisphenol-F with four, six or eight molecules of triethylenetetraamine (TETA). They report simulations of modulus and volume vs. temperature behavior from which they determine a glass transition temperature that is in excellent agreement with their reported experimental values. Faulon [7] has developed a method for polymer building as beads or sites on a mesh. He uses appropriate chain statistics and attempts to build a minimum energy configuration. After the build process chemical details can be included to configure as an atomistic model. The method is demonstrated with a linear chain but is expected to be able to build cross-linked

thermoset systems as well. The approach is also supposed to avoid the unphysical high energy system that cannot be minimized in a reasonable time. He touches on all the problems expected with polymer building including, the inability to simulate the reaction chemistry, equilibrating the resulting glassy structure, proper chain statistics and excessive computational time. Another lattice method is presented by Kotelyanskii et al [8]. They note that in order to avoid the complicated compaction and anneal procedure associated with building a polymer structure directly or the highly strained bond condition due to “reacting” monomer units in the periodic cell; they have developed a lattice building algorithm that includes the introduction atomistic detail. The method is used to build a linear polymer, stiffness of monomer units and branched or cross-linked structures will present additional difficulty for the build system.

Doherty et al [9] also present a lattice method and demonstrate its use with a thermoset system. They use their method to construct a cross-linked polymethacrylate dental adhesive polymer. The monomers, bisphenol-A glycidyl dimethacrylate (bisGMA) and triethylene glycol dimethacrylate (TEGMDA) are placed in a random rotational orientation on a lattice. The monomer mix is then energy minimized followed by additional simulations to mix the monomers. A polymerization process involving reaction of a single connection bond followed by a simulation for system relaxation is performed sequentially. Reaction sites can be selected arbitrarily or based on close approach. Hamerton et al [10] recognize the need for atomistic detail in their assessment of three different dicyanate monomers, they note that interpretation of the analysis allowed discrimination between two of the structures and provided support for the potential to use “in-silico” synthesis methods for future technology development. They began by constructing low molecular weight polycyanurates on an atom by atom basis and then used the crystal builder functionality within the Cerius 2 software suite to produce a three dimensional cell for properties analysis. Finally, Vogt and Hernandez [11] present another lattice based polymer growth method that is supposed to account for the steric effects expected in a high density non-equilibrium polymerization.

Reactive molecular dynamics programs such as the procedure described by Stoliarov et al [12] for the decomposition of polyisobutylene have been written and could also be formatted for polymerization. The programs available are for thermoplastic systems only. Tsige and Taylor [13] are using the polymer builder library in the Materials Studio®, commercial software available from Accelrys. The method involves selection of an appropriate fragment or monomer structure from a library of available monomers. The head and tail or connection sites for reaction as in the procedure outlined in [9] are labeled.

EXPERIMENTAL

We use molecular modeling techniques to predict the physical properties of the engineering polymer within the composite including the maximum strain invariants. The accuracy of such simulations depend on two main aspects, described in the following subsections, i) the force field used to describe the interactions between atoms and ii) the use of atomic structures that accurately represent the complex microstructure and topology of the material. The following subsections describe the MD simulations carried out to characterize the deformation of the polymer and extract the strain invariants.

All polymer building and molecular dynamics simulations were accomplished using Materials Studio (Accelrys Inc.) software and the associated periodic structure building tool – Amorphous Cell®. Molecular dynamics simulations were performed

with Discover using the COMPASS force field. The polymer building process consists of several steps outlined below:

1. Configure an n-mer of the polymer in order to identify bonds that will span a charge group. These will be the logical monomer blocks and the individual structures will be capped with separately typed hydrogen's.
2. Build the appropriate seed and generation structures, type, assign charge groups, select connect and head atoms and select backbone.
3. When building structures in item 2 above, remove the hydrogen's at the heavy atom join points, type and assign charge groups. Then add hydrogen's back onto the atomistic structure, select, type and assign each hydrogen as a separate charge group. Open dendrimer dialog and select the hydrogen's as connect and/or head atom(s) as appropriate.
4. Export the structures to either the dendrimer seed or structure file, path is: C:/programfiles/Accelrys/msmodeling4.1/data/resources/polymer builder/dendrimer/seed or structure
5. Use dendrimer build function to construct a polymer a generation at a step. Relaxation or rearrangement of the growing chain may be necessary to prevent spearing or catenation.

In order to maintain the computational and non-bond force calculation accuracy, a monomer build method that splits the epoxy and amine at a neutral charge group boundary is necessary. The amine hydrogen-epoxy ring opening reaction is included in the monomer structure so that the fragment built has the appearance of the linkage as it would be in the cured polymer and not as the individual monomer. The charge group boundary within the cured system is shown in figure 3, and is between the hydroxyl methylene group and the methylene group that was originally the less substituted carbon in the oxirane ring. Charge group assignment therefore consists of the methylenes attached to the amine nitrogen plus the adjoining carbon of the phenylene ring and hydroxyl methylene group. To indicate where the reaction is to take place, the hydrogen atoms that will be removed during the polymerization are designated as either a connecting point or head atom if it represents the location that is to be added as a subsequent generation. The hydrogen's are also treated as separate charge groups. The structures can be stored in special files for recalling whenever polymer building is necessary.

Using the dendrimer build method has the additional flexibility of removing and reinstalling the connect points after each generation providing a means to build "defect" structures. The method outlined is similar to the von Ferber and Blumen [21] technique. Since the bond sites are also designated by hydrogen atoms that have been assigned as a separate charge group, they can be manually connected if appropriate between additions of generations. The defect structures we built in this fashion, each with a different theme. Defect structures one and two are an attempt to assess cluster formation during polymerization, defect three is assessing steric effects and the cyclic structure contains some intramolecular bonding.

The structure determinations of Corezzi and Fioretto [20] and [24] and Volponi et al [25] outline the random nature of step polymerization and the formation of clusters. They define a cluster as a set of bonded monomers present in the system at a certain extent of polymerization. As cluster formation expands, they interact at their peripheries causing a slowing of the dynamics of the reacting species and the necessity for an increase in cooperative motion for continued polymerization. Eventually an arrested structure of interconnected clusters results with additional chemical bond formation

possible only through diffusion of reactive sites. Glassy freezing occurs when there is steric and diffusional limits on development of additional network structure. Extensive cyclic formation is not likely, due to the stiff components because the adventitious alignment of reactive sites is most likely a low probability event. Additional support for the structural concept comes from the rapid reduction in correlation between the succeeding generations, Zapperi et al [22] and Dusek et al [23] note that correlation is not very strong. Wu [16] also notes that spatial correlation to any sub chain or structure chosen at random vanishes within less than ten units. Wu and Bauer [18] note that a network can deform by unfolding without a dramatic change in the distance between cross-links.

Molecular dynamics simulations of materials, while providing a very detailed description, are limited in size and atom count; our simulation cells contain one or two polymer chains, with typical simulation cell of about 3.5 to 4 nm on the side. We impose periodic boundary conditions to avoid the presence of free surfaces that would otherwise dominate the response of the material for such small samples. The COMPASS force field [6] is used to describe the atomic interactions. COMPASS has been parameterized to account for finite temperature effects and more accurately predict replicate condensed phase properties. COMPASS is a refinement of the PCFF forcefield and has been extensively used in polymer simulations and is an extension of the class II forcefield of Hagler et al [1, 2, 3] one of the first to make extensive use of ab initio quantum mechanics calculations to parameterize the valence interactions of “internals”.

Figure 1, Group based cutoffs positions and methodology for selection of monomer configuration.

The configuration of high functionality, cross-linked polymer structures such as epoxies are controlled by the variety of potential chemical reactions that are influenced by the size, reactivity and stiffness of the monomer species and the specific stoichiometry. Actual polymer networks are not likely to exhibit material uniformity and symmetry, but rather exhibit variations in both composition and structure. These variations within actual networks are due in part to the fluctuations in concentrations of the monomer ingredients. For the purpose of this study, two epoxy resin systems were evaluated. One system is a commercially available material for which we were kindly provided the chemistry and the other is a formulation developed by us. Our in-house

developed system consists of a 4,4-DDS hardener mixed with 1:1 stoichiometry with a mix of Bisphenol-A and Tactix 756 epoxies. The monomer molecules were built using the Materials Studio (vers4.4) and the polymer structure was constructed using the Dendrimer building functionality.

Cubic periodic cells containing about 5500 to 6000 atoms were built with the Amorphous Cell module of Materials Studio. In order to increase the building success rate, the cells are initially constructed at low a density of 0.4 grams/cc and at a temperature of 650K. 25 configurations were constructed and the nine lowest energy structures were selected for additional energy minimization. We then used the Discover molecular dynamics module to anneal the samples and generate equilibrated structures at ambient conditions. The temperature for all simulations was equilibrated with the Anderson thermostat and the applied pressure for the isobaric simulations was controlled with the Berendsen barostat. The sample is cooled down to T=300K in steps of 50K; at each temperature we perform a 50 ps long simulation at constant volume and temperature (NVT ensemble) followed by a constant pressure and volume (NPT) run for 50 ps. As described in Table 1 we increase the pressure during the annealing process to achieve compaction. After annealing the energy minimized periodic cells were then used as a starting point for a 250 ps production runs using NPT dynamics at one atmosphere (Anderson thermostat and Berendsen barostat) with periodic boundary conditions. A snapshot of the trajectory was stored every 2.5 ps. The last ten frames of the trajectory were then examined and the structure with the highest density was selected for analysis of properties.

NVT for 50 ps at 650K (Equilibration)
NPT for 50 ps at 650K and 0.1 GPa (Initial compaction)
NVT for 50 ps at 500K (Equilibration)
NPT for 50 ps at 500K and 0.25 GPa (Additional compaction)
NVT for 50 ps at 450K (Equilibration)
NPT for 50 ps at 400K and 0.0001 GPa (Reduce to 1 atmosphere)
NVT for 50 ps at 300K (Equilibration)
NPT for 50 ps at 300K and 0.0001 GPa (Equilibration)
Minimization to convergence level < 0.001 kcal/mol/Å

Table 1, Dynamics Anneal Simulation Protocol

Once the molecular model of the polymer has been constructed, we interrogate its deformation characteristics with the goal of determining their character and assessing yield phenomena. To characterize phenomena involving volume changes we perform a isobaric volume vs temperature scan. The room temperature minimized cell is first heated to 800K and then stepwise cooling of the periodic cells from T=800 K to T=100 K in steps of 25K every 40 ps. The cell dimensions of the last 20% of each 40 ps simulation are averaged and reported. The intercept of a linear fit to the data between 100° and 300° and 600° and 800° was taken as the glass transition with the linear fit of glassy region used as the thermal contraction behavior. The critical dilatational deformation or J_1 at room temperature is calculated by determining the amount of volumetric contraction from the glass transition, table 2 presents the calculation of the value of J_1 for the cooling and heating cycle for the two systems studied.

System	Glass Transition, K		CTE, /°K		J_1	
	sim	expt	sim	expt	sim	expt
Commercial	446	428	60.1×10^{-6}	54.7×10^{-6}	.0265	.025
Formula # 1	465	464	59.7×10^{-6}	59.8×10^{-6}	.030	.027

Table 2, Thermal properties for the resin systems studied

Distortional deformation is a mechanism that involves a shape change without undergoing a volume change. The distortional capability of a polymer network involves the ability of the molecular backbone to rotate through dihedral angles. These rotations increase the ability of the system to absorb strain energy by means of a dissipative process. Capaldi[4] et al note that during deformation there is a significant increase in polymer backbone torsional transitions through rotation of dihedral angles and that the percolation of this mobility leads to a yield event. The simulations of Malandro and Lacks [5] support the concept that these torsional rearrangements are dissipative events that are manifested by the non-linear stress-strain response. The critical von Mises event represents the maximum level of torsional rearrangement before the onset of flow or the complete disappearance of local energy minimums due to the relaxation to new local minimums. Simulation of the process is accomplished through a series of increasing load uni-directional compression tests until yield. Yield in this instance is defined as the strain at maximum applied stress.

Figure 2, Simulation (filled squares) compared with experimental uni-directional compression test (filled diamonds) of an epoxy resin consisting of 1:1 stoichiometry triglycidyl p-aminophenol and 4, 4' diaminodiphenylsulfone. Data reported in: S. Behzadi and F.R. Jones, "Yielding Behavior of Model Epoxy Matrices for Fiber Reinforced Composites: Effect of Strain Rate and Temperature" *Journal of Macromolecular Science, Pt B: Physics* Vol 44 pp 993-1005 (2005).

In order to simulate the compression yield event, we developed a molecular dynamics uni-directional loading protocol that provides the best replication of experimental data. Numerous schemes were evaluated and compared with experimental results as shown in the figure 2 example taken from Behzadi and Jones [7]. The method applies uni-directional loads to a periodic structure with a series of increasing stress NPT dynamics simulations using a Parrinello barostat that allows the shape and volume of cell to change so that the internal stress will match the externally applied stress. Each subsequent stress level starts with the energy equilibrated cubic cell rather than a

compacted cell from the previous load cycle. Cell dimensional changes are monitored in order to determine the level of compaction for calculation of the strain and to insure reaching an equilibrium level of compaction. Results of the testing performed in the three principle cell directions and on nine distinct configurations for a total of 27 tests were averaged to determine the yield strain. Rather than monitor the maximum and minor principle strains, the yield strain is factored by 1.5 to account for the transverse strain measures and reported as the critical von Mises strain. The compression simulation results for the two systems studied are presented in figure 3. Based on the simulated yield strains, the predicted critical distortional deformations are presented in table 3.

Figure 2, Uni-directional compression strength simulation for Formula # 1; load control shown as filled squares, displacement control shown as open squares. Commercial resin simulation, load control shown as filled circles and displacement control shown as open circles.

System	Critical Distortional Invariant	
	expt	sim
Formula # 1	0.25	0.26
Commercial System	0.203	0.198

Table 3, Critical Distortional Invariants, Experimental values derived from analysis of 10° off-axis lamina tensile test, simulated values derived from neat resin uni-directional compression test.

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